

**Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich - DSc.,
professor of the institute International
School of Finance Technology and Science**

Abstract. *The article analyzes the indicators of food production as a result of the reforms in the development of the food industry in our country based on statistical data. Also, scientific-practical recommendations on ensuring food safety on the basis of sustainable development of the food industry have been developed.*

Keywords: *industrial enterprises, food industry, food security, economic reforms, sustainable development.*

Introduction.

It is equally clear to all of us that climate change and various changes in economic and political processes, which are worrying their countries, are causing problems related to food security. In this regard, today, along with social protection of the population of our country, the sustainable development of the food industry is one of the most urgent tasks in ensuring food security, which is their primary need.

Decision PQ-146 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to implement the tasks set in the dialogue with entrepreneurs who grow, manufacture and export agricultural and food products" and On the basis of the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to rapidly develop the food industry of the Republic and provide the population with high-quality food products" PQ-4821 issues of taking measures to exempt imported raw materials and packaging equipment and items from customs duties for export" [1,2].

Literature review.

Professor In his research on ensuring food security by Khpabulqasimov, "The policy of ensuring food security of the state is to rationally harmonize the levels of self-sufficiency in food products and their import, to provide the population of the country with food creation of guaranteed possibilities of supply with products" was discussed[3].

In the research conducted by S. Alikulov and other researchers, the problems of ensuring food security by increasing the volume of food production in agriculture by farmers and landowners have been shown [4].

Based on the above urgent tasks, the impact of various changes in the process of ensuring food safety through the development of the food industry was conducted on the basis of national and international statistical sources. Based on the analysis of the indicators of food production, practical recommendations were developed by analyzing the methodological aspects of ensuring food safety.

Analysis and results. In today's global climate change, one of the important issues is to increase the attention to ensure food security as the main problem of concern of the world community. In this regard, it is appropriate to consistently continue the reforms in the field of sustainable development of the food industry in our country, further improvement of the activities of food enterprises. Therefore,

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it is necessary to pay more attention to agricultural entities in the supply of agricultural products, which are suppliers of the food industry. Also, for many food-importing countries today, the high level of major risk creates a serious situation mainly as a food safety policy.

World food industry and food price index. the world the food market is traditionally characterized by high volume and low margins. Today, the brands created in the world food industry directly change the wishes of consumers of industrial products. The total revenue of the global food market in 2022 was 8.670 billion US dollars. Japan spent the most on food at \$5,365 per capita.

According to international statistical sources, In South Korea, the total production value of the food industry in 2022 is approximately 3.15% of the country's GDP, an increase of 2.91% compared to 2021. In the last three years, the country has seen an increase in its value as a share of the gross domestic product compared to previous years.[3].

Figure 1. Annual food price index by category worldwide from 2000 to 2024[3]

The food industry, one of the largest sectors in the United States, has been affected by retail sales. Mainly this process has been influenced directly by the impact of the global pandemic, food inflation and changes in consumer behavior that have shaped the industrial landscape. For example, due to the increased demand for online shopping in the United States, total retail e-commerce share of food and beverage sales It grew from 9.3 percent in 2017 to nearly 16 percent in 2023 and is expected to reach 21.5 percent by 2027.

Looking at the annual food price index by category worldwide from 2000 to 2024, According to data provided by FAO, the Food Price Index (FFPI) averaged 124.7 points in 2023, which is a decrease of 20 points compared to 2022. The highest value of the index in the last ten years was reached in 2022 (Figure 1).

Analysis of the state of the food industry in Uzbekistan.

Food products include production-edible agricultural, forestry and fishery products (food), soft drinks, mineral waters and other bottled waters. According to the results of January-December 2023, the share of food production in the manufacturing industry was 11.8%, and compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, the physical volume index increased by 6.2% and production volume 65 174.7 bln. corresponded to soums (Figure 2).

Conclusion.

At this point, it should be said that the need for the development of the food industry is the increase in the number of the world's population, global climate changes, the occurrence of water

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shortages, the salinization of agricultural lands, and the increase in the volume of various natural disasters. - affects food safety, which naturally leads to an increase in the price of food products. In our opinion, food industry development food products it is appropriate to introduce mechanisms of economic stimulation by the state to increase the volume of production and ensure the economic stability of production enterprises.

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